

INVESTIGATION OF THE FAILURE BEHAVIOR OF SHORT-FIBER-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS WITH MOLDED IN HOLES

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1 Introduction

Injection molded tensile bars made of glass-fiber-reinforced Polyamide 66 (33% fiber volume fraction) with molded in 4 mm holes were subjected to tensile load in order to study their failure behavior. Furthermore, Digital Image Correlation (DIC) Testing was accomplished to investigate the tensile strain fields on the surface of the tensile bars. In addition, injection molding simulations with Moldex3D were carried out to generate fiber orientation and stiffness data for an ABAQUS-Model. This model was used to simulate the tensile tests in order to compare FEM and DIC-Results for tensile strain. Finally, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed to investigate the micro-failure of the fracture surfaces.

2 Results

Besides the classical failure at the smallest cross section at the hole, a second, competitive failure mode around the hole could be observed. It is illustrated in Figure (1). A resulting tensile strain field of the DIC-Analysis just before the failure of the part is shown in Figure (2). In contrast to a usual strain field of an isotropic material, the strain maxima are displaced towards the gate side of the hole. The failure line was modeled and data for the tensile strain was extracted. The geometry of the failure trajectory was examined in the 3D ABAQUS-Model. Information about tensile strain, stiffness components and fiber orientation were extracted in the thickness direction for the mold surfaces and the mid plane of the modeled bar. The

strain results along the failure path were found to be similar through the thickness. For the top surface, the strain data of the DIC and FEM-Analysis along the normalized fracture length are compared in Figure (3). The shapes of the graphs are very similar with the strain extrema in nearly the same locations. The fiber orientation and stiffness data were analyzed. It could be observed that the fibers tend to align in the transverse direction of the flow in front of the stagnation point at the hole. Moving towards the edges of the failure line, the fiber orientation becomes tangent to the hole and thereby, aligned in the direction of load. This change in fiber orientation in the regions of maximum strain along the fracture line is connected with a gradient in tensile stiffness, which was confirmed by the extracted stiffness data.

Finally, the fracture surface was investigated by SEM. In the mentioned regions of high tensile strains along the failure line, ductile matrix failure in connection with fiber breakage could be found, as seen in Figure (4). The other regions were dominated by brittle matrix failure. These observations agree in terms of the matrix behavior with a micro-failure model developed by Sato et al. [1]. The authors investigated the failure of Polyamide 66 with 30% glass fibers in-situ by SEM-Analysis. According to their results, ductile behavior in the initiation region of failure first occurs. Then the opening crack becomes critical and brittle matrix failure.

Fig. 1. Failure around the hole for the investigated tensile bars

Fig. 2. DIC-Tensile strain field with modeled failure line

Fig. 3. Comparison of the tensile strain along the modeled failure lines

Fig. 3. Observed micro-failure in the area of maximum tensile strain along the fracture path

3 Conclusions

The observation of the described fracture around the hole illustrated that for the investigated injection molded parts microstructure can be the dominating reason for failure. This is an interesting result since the usual expectation is a fracture at the smallest cross section at the hole.

By further investigations, it could be shown that both the DIC- and the FEM-results agree in the regions of maximum strain along the modeled fracture line. In these regions, ductile matrix failure was observed by SEM. According to a micro-failure model of a very similar material [1], this ductile behavior displays the initiation region of failure. Based on the results of a molding simulation, a gradient in tensile stiffness due to a changing fiber orientation was determined in the mentioned areas. Therefore, stress concentrations on the micro-scale are a probable reason for the occurred failure around the hole.

References

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